

Digital Identity Systems Utilization Across Countries : A Survey

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Abstract

This paper presents a literature review of digital identity systems and their uses as conveyed by governments, it maps how IDs are used across countries for verification and disbursement of services to their citizens. Digital identity cards issued by nations today usually consist of identifying details of a citizen coupled with their biometric and demographic information. The advent of such id systems was built to solve the problem of conducting seamless identity validations which later evolved into amplifying its use cases across a host of services both public and private. Digital identity systems have become increasingly critical for citizens to fulfill their needs; from opening a bank account to receiving welfare from the government, confirming one's identity via said id is the new normal. In this survey, we first present how identity systems catered to the use cases they were created to solve initially and advance to their evolution, covering how they are expanding to handle more citizen needs. This includes assessing their usage across financial, welfare, governance, travel, trade and more. This is followed by assessing citizen experience with said identity systems and further providing some observations on the same. While ID initiatives aim to fulfill such ambitious goals, the process of adaptation by citizens plays a key role in the success of such initiatives. This is further corroborated by observations from countries Estonia, Malaysia, EU and Japan. Aligning the vision behind the creation of IDs with the metric of citizen acceptance could help drive effective adoption of ID-systems.

Policy Significance Statement

This paper analyzes various countries' identity cards across countries and sheds light on their varied methods of usage, that is, their use cases. It further delves into what could be made better about a country's digital identity card. This paper provides insights and observations based on real time issues noted about a said identity card. The suggestions and observations from this paper could be used by policymakers to further mould better identification systems by taking into account the unique insights from each country's identification system. This paper suggests better versions of identity cards could be possible when the ID card utilization process is malleable according to citizen needs and citizen comfort; enabling easier utilization and access to said ID cards.

Introduction

Identity systems have always been crucial and play a key role in ensuring a citizen is granted recognition and access to services from the state. Digitizing such mechanisms to create a digital identity through which citizens can validate their identity via respective citizen personal, demographic and even biometric data has allowed for an ecosystem where governments can avail such id systems as a single source of truth to disburse varied services to citizens in a relatively less timespan by exploiting such digital validations. Identity validation in the digital form aimed to fulfill the goal of providing enhanced interoperability, convenience and accessibility to those availing such ids and choosing to receive services from the state through them. As a result, many governments across the world have decided to utilize digital identity systems across multiple spheres of citizen life. Their implementation of such systems and their varied areas can be seen further below later.

Identification systems attempt to play a key role in achieving a set goal in a specific circumstance by distinguishing people to achieve said goal. While utilization of identification systems has attempted to do the same across time, there is marked variance in the methods utilized to achieve different goals. Be it among the Maori people of New Zealand, who utilized identity markers in the form of tattoos to signify their status, membership in a particular group and even ancestry⁹¹, the Greeks who branded slaves to distinguish them or the Thracians who distinguished their higher status through identifying markers like tattoos⁹⁴; identification has served to achieve specific goals across time. Varied purposes served by IDs can also be seen in the case of the identifying documents provided to the subjects of King Henry V of England in the form of passports; which enabled them to prove their identity in foreign countries, along with receiving security in said country⁹¹; it can be observed that identity as a check has been utilized for serving purposes from assigning people to a segment, to providing them with safety.

More use cases of identification systems could be observed in the 19th century when Napoleon decided to make governance more efficient; with him also setting forth a requirement for ID documents among workers after the french revolution⁹². His reforms encouraged other countries like the Ottoman Empire to adopt ID as a tool to build state capabilities⁹². It could be observed that enabling the state to achieve its aims was one more use case of identity documents from the UK's example too. While times of heightened risk like the world wars have led to a spike in the adoption of ID in the past across countries like the UK (where male citizens eligible for national service were identified using the same), it is also observed that linking ID with critical services like food rations simultaneously led to adoption and also mission creep with ID being utilized for services from health services to pension claims and even police enquiries by the state⁹³. Identity systems also served as tools to foster sovereignty, which is observed in the case of the ID implementations of Hong Kong and Taiwan where ID's were issued to citizens in an attempt to foster sovereignty and reduce immigration⁹³.

From systems which served the purpose of distinguishing one's membership in a group, identity systems have evolved into tools which enable citizens to access services provided by their governments. From the case of the mission creep observed in the UK's plan for national register during world war two, to the case of the prevalence of identity documents or cards to access services offered by governments today; it can be observed that an identifying document has become integral to access public services offered to citizens by governments today. These services could range from accessing food rations, to health services and would cover almost all of the services offered by the state; ranging from paying one's taxes, to claiming welfare benefits and even acting as an identifier which serves to distinguish a citizen's death (a death certificate number).

An example of identity cards acting as enabling tools in a citizen's private sphere could be seen in the case of Finland where, the social identity cards which had been updated with tax numbers not only led to five hundred million euros increase in tax payments alone but a 9% hike in salary payments too⁹⁵. The said ID cards served as identifying documents to enable workers to identify themselves and further work in a construction site, allowing their employer to identify their employees and be aware of the personnel on site and disburse payments accordingly⁹⁵. Another case of identity documents usage in the private sphere could be the example of Swedish banks issuing identity documents to help their customers prove their identity while utilizing the bank's checks' ⁹⁶. This ID which aimed to solve a single use case had later evolved to become an officially accepted ID too⁹⁶.

It could also be observed that enforcing ID usage in private organizations, as observed with the case of a school in Sweden, which needed teachers and parents to log into the school's services through the state provided electronic ID, (used to access services provided by state and also perform private activities like shopping) was met with resistance as there was reticence from teachers' about utilizing their private eID's in a professional setting⁹⁷. A similar phenomenon could be seen with the staff of the hospital who were asked to do the same, and were further incentivized by linking access to auxiliary services like parking, coffee and more with staff's respective eID and further observed noticeable resistance from staff⁹⁷.

An Ideal Identity system

The varied existing identity systems across countries and the gaps observed in them raise the question of the possibility of creating an ideal identity system, at least in theory. To define an ideal identity system, defining the expectations and requirements from such a system would help eke out the formulation of the same. Below are the possible functions an ideal identity system would achieve and adhere to.

Identity validation : This functionality of the identity system would achieve the goal of ensuring that a citizen's identity would be validated seamlessly. This would further contain the process of registering citizens initially, which would consist of the local government body official utilizing

existing citizen identity proofs to verify and register citizens and further provide them with an ID. The citizen registration process would be successful if the citizen identity proofs and the respective citizen information from them are verified by the said official and the citizen biometrics are enrolled in an access controlled, decentralized system with zero knowledge proof. After registering, citizens could further prove their identity by validating their biometric identity.

- Requirements :
 - Citizen identifying data (like name and demographic information)
 - Existing citizen identification proof
 - Citizen biometric identification

- Assumptions :
 - Decentralised system, data is not stored in a central database and is further not shared across government bodies
 - Access controlled, official is not able to access all data
 - Zero knowledge proof, citizen data is not accessible to any party unless consent to access a specific data point is given by a citizen

- **Authentication** : The ID could be authenticated by verifying actors based on the citizen information (in ID) and further be deduplicated to uniquely identify citizens accordingly.
 - Requirements:
 - Citizen identifying information : biometric information, citizen demographic information
 - Assumptions:
 - Authentication occurs only after citizen provides consent to an identification request and would fail otherwise

- **Revocable Consent** : This functionality would involve the citizen's providing consent to a body, it could be a particular data point of their ID or data points of their choice in said ID. The verifying actor would further have access to said data for a limited period of time to authenticate citizen identity and further be unable to access the same after the given consent time-limit.
 - Requirements:
 - Factors needed : Citizen consent or rejection to a request, consent time-limit, citizen data
 - Citizens can view, track, provide time bound consent; or reject requests for their identifying information
 - Assumptions :
 - Citizen information is encrypted and no single actor has access to all citizen identifying information

- Citizens can provide partial consent, that is; share access to certain data points of his ID.
- **Updation** : The ID data can be modified by citizens according to their changing demographic or physical characteristics.
 - Requirements:
 - Citizens providing existing proof of identifying information they wish to change and citizens validating themselves (ex: via their biometric) to complete the updation
 - Assumptions :
 - Citizens have multiple modes of ID validations available to them, be it via biometrics or a one time password of their mobile number (or email), or through even their voice.

Utilization of Digital Identity Systems Across Countries

India

The Aadhaar card is the digital identity card availed by citizens of India which by rule of law is not mandatory for most cases, apart from linking it to PAN card (which is used to ensure citizen fiscal dues are met) and a citizen cannot be denied welfare or benefits from the state if he lacks aadhaar²⁸. This digital identity system which enables citizens to avail resources from public distribution systems has its applications across multiple spheres today namely,

Finance : In the sphere of finance, filing income tax returns as a citizen would not be possible unless said citizen has linked his PAN card with aadhaar; while this has been mandated, actions like opening a bank account, transacting online, knowing one's credit information or even investing in the stock market are all activities which allow citizens to avail aadhaar to digitally verify themselves to move forth towards their intended goal¹. Even availing insurance, if we take the case of the insurance subsidy Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana, allows citizens to avail the subsidy by utilizing aadhaar².

Travel : Usage of aadhaar card is incentivized by government across the spectrum of citizen travel needs like applying for passport³ or even booking a train ticket⁴, perks like sped up processing time in the case of passport and allowing citizens to book an increased number of tickets per month are few incentives to ensure aadhaar utilization by citizens. Apart from these activities like acquiring a driving license⁵ or even checking into a hotel⁶ are some processes which accept citizens to avail aadhaar to validate their identity.

Welfare : The welfare disbursement by government requires welfare recipients to furnish his or her respective aadhaar to avail a subsidy provided by the state, according to Indian law, if an aadhaar is not furnished, the recipient should be provided the welfare benefits by assessing his identity through an alternative mechanism¹. Aadhaar can be seen as a requirement across various subsidies namely,

Food subsidies: Some of the schemes like Prime Minister Ujjwala Yojana which ensure women below the poverty line are provided with LPG gas cylinder connections and the scheme which allows for availing subsidized food through ration card; needs citizen to provide their respective aadhaar cards for availing their benefits seamlessly⁷.

Child development : Subsidies like the Midday Meal scheme⁸ aimed at bolstering nutritional needs of primary school children at government schools or subsidies related to helping children pursue education via scholarships⁹ are some of the many which call for welfare recipients to validate identity through the aadhaar card. The other spectrum of schemes focused on maternity benefits¹⁰ and child development¹¹ are some areas where the usage of aadhaar is required to access said benefits.

The aadhaar card also serves as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left

<i>Health</i>	For Accessing: ABHA ¹² health records, health ID card, healthcare facilities ¹³
<i>Pension</i>	For accessing: the employee provident fund or PF ¹⁴ and the Digital Life Certificate ¹⁵ which acts as a proof of citizen existence (which further enables a citizen to the PF)
<i>Land</i>	For availing home development fund ¹⁶ from government, or for Registering land in some cases ¹⁷
<i>Employment</i>	For accessing: MGNREGA scheme payouts ¹⁸ , or for Biometric attendance for government employees (which needs said employee's aadhaar to prove attendance) ¹⁹
<i>Agriculture</i>	For accessing : Soil health card scheme ²⁰ which provides soil health report to farmers, and also Crop insurance ²¹ support

<i>Social security</i>	For accessing : Benefits which support elderly, disabled, widows via schemes like the National Social Assistance Programme ²²
<i>Governance</i>	For signing e-filed documents in e-courts ²³
<i>Trade</i>	For Registering a business, availing skill upgradation and credit support from schemes like PM Vishwakarma ²⁴
<i>Communication</i>	For Registering a SIM ²⁵ , or a data wallet like DigiLocker ²⁶
<i>Identity</i>	For proving : one's identity, residency ²⁷ ; legally binding signature ²³ For accessing ID for Aliens : Can be issued if individual has stayed in the country for more than 182 days ²⁸ <i>Voting</i> : Can link aadhaar to voter id to further prove one's identity ²⁹
<i>Electoral inclusion</i>	<i>roll</i> The Aadhaar card can now be used as the identity document by citizens for inclusion in the voter list ⁹⁸ . This is possible due to the Supreme court's ruling advising Election Commission of India (ECI) on the same while ECI was performing the Special Intensive Revision of voters' list for the state of Bihar.

Observations :

While Aadhaar has been offered to India's citizens with a vision to enable effective service delivery and has today evolved into a version with multi-pronged use cases; it is important to understand the real time effects of citizen utilization of aadhaar to further assess areas or factors which can be improved and identify successes which could be replicated, if feasible.

An example of this could be how a study conducted to understand how distribution of food subsidies positively or negatively impacted government and beneficiaries found that in one state (andhra pradesh) beneficiaries were positively impacted and government expenditure reduced and in another state (Jharkhand) the reduction in government expenditure negatively impacted beneficiaries³⁰. The study notes that this was due to differences in state level policy prioritization (with AP prioritizing beneficiary experience and Jharkhand focusing on curbing corruption). While it is clear that a synergy of both states' priorities is important to deliver benefits; it needn't be at the cost of one another.

The observation here could be to understand the need for creating mechanisms to achieve malleable executory or process bodies which are prepared to adapt to citizen needs or situations

which might not necessarily fit the conventional process flow of delivery a service. Example, in Jharkhand beneficiaries were denied access to benefits if they failed to seed their aadhaar; creating pathways to enable citizen seeding by enabling the bodies responsible for seeding to be malleable to unique citizen use cases or pain points and further molding themselves to enable successful delivery could impact all actors involved positively.

Another study points out how welfare benefits related to health that citizens should receive were not utilized effectively due to problems related to accessing aadhaar which further curbed citizens from availing said health benefits³¹. While the Indian Supreme court states that an alternative form of identity verification should be utilized in cases where aadhaar is unavailable²⁸, mechanisms to fill that gap, example utilizing an id form which a specific set of beneficiaries are already using (ex: MGNREGA Job Card which also acts as an ID , in the case of citizens enrolled in the MGNREGA employment provision scheme) need to become the norm. Another observation, this one to curb possible misuse of health data would be delinking aadhaar from health services and ensuring citizen health information is restricted solely to a citizen health card. This could ensure sensitive health information of citizens does not get interlinked with the multiple other use cases of aadhaar and further ensure citizen privacy.

Estonia

The digital identity system in Estonia complements the physical national ID and aims to provide citizens with services like digital signing and digital authentication among many; the digital identity card or eID can be used across a wide range of citizen touchpoints as of today from shopping to even voting online³².

Finance : The identity card enables citizens to log into bank accounts³², file Income Tax³³ returns allowing them to further perform secure transactions via online banking by enabling them to verify their identity via the electronic form of the digital identity card.

Travel : In the sphere of travel, the digital ID not only acts as a valid travel document, the limits of its validity cover the entire European region area³².

E-services : A large number of e-services provided by the government are made available 24 hours a day³⁶, they can be accessed using the digital identity format of the ID card³². An example would be the e-child sport which disburses money needed for children's sports needs³⁵

The ID card also serves as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left

<i>Health</i>	For Accessing : Services like e-prescription and e-health records ³⁴
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<i>Trade</i>	For Registering a business; can be utilized for paying bills or even shopping ³²
<i>Identification</i>	For proving : one's identity and digitally signing ³² For accessing ID for Aliens : Foreign nationals can also be issued a digital ID to conduct business ³²
<i>Voting</i>	For Voting : Citizens can i-vote using their digital id ³⁶

Observations :

In the process of analyzing how citizens avail ID services in real time, we often find out what citizens' expectations are from ID; the case of this matching the state's envisioned agenda behind ID or not, is often an interesting tell which could convey the next possible step in improving an ID. One study which analyzed citizen priorities with respect to Estonia's ID found that citizens tended to prioritize convenience, speed, security and co-existence of multiple validation options based on their setting³⁷. While Estonia is working on catering to the same; an observation here would be to note that while a majority defines the variety of convenience they prefer this variety might not be feasible for another minority citizen set (ex: elderly with little preference to access digital mode of services). Being cognizant of the same and ensuring delivery of state services via one kind of pathway (ex: digital mode) would not happen at the cost of deprioritising pathways of another kind of service delivery (perhaps preferred by the minority citizen set) would help form an effective service delivery model.

Bangladesh

National ID or NID is the identity card issued to citizens of Bangladesh. While it was initially conceived as part of a project which aimed to create a comprehensive electoral roll³⁹; it has now expanded to enable citizens to access various services provided by the government, ranging from accessing government benefits to registering for a SIM using the NID⁴⁰.

Finance : In the sphere of finance, the national ID is utilized for opening of bank accounts, it is also used for availing loans; and even withdrawing money from ATMs or performing internet banking⁴⁰.

Travel : The national identity card can be utilized by citizens to verify their identity while they are applying for a passport where it serves as a valid form of identity proof for the citizens applying to said services⁴⁰.

Services : The national identity card can be utilized to access the welfare benefits and services (across fields from registrations to grants and more) provided by the government, it has been

used for citizen identification and validation increase the effectiveness of service delivery; and an example is the case of the government its improving service delivery by identifying and validating citizens on its service delivery portal to further deliver services without inefficiency⁴³.

The National ID also serves as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left

<i>Pension</i>	For accessing: the employee provident fund or PF ⁴⁶
<i>Agriculture</i>	For accessing : Agricultural import and export, for consultations on soil health ⁴⁴
<i>Trade</i>	For Registration of a business, for renewing license for sale of goods ⁴⁵
<i>Education</i>	For Accessing student scholarships ⁴⁶

Observation:

While observing the history of how digital ID came to be in Bangladesh, it is seen that it was built as a by product to the country's original goal of creating a reliable voters' list and while it had laws which dissuade citizens from providing falsified data while enrolling for their ID; it lacked laws which protect citizen privacy with respect to the ID information in the database³⁹. An observation here would be to understand that while it is feasible to approach service delivery (in this case, provision of an ID) with safeguards to ensure effectiveness of delivery; creating an approach which is built around enunciating, prioritizing and balancing state and citizen requirements and further realizing the same could prove to be more effective.

Malaysia

The MyKad is the identity card which was initially introduced to protect the country against communist risks; while the ID aims to serve as an identification proof along with catering to other citizen use cases; its main uses revolved around using it as a valid travel document for travel near neighboring countries, and the government also aimed to utilize the card for the storage of health information.

Finance : In the sphere of finance, the applications of MyKad can be seen in its usage for withdrawing money by utilizing it at ATMs, it also enables citizens to perform digital transactions by acting as an electronic purse⁴⁹.

Travel : While the MyKad acts as a valid travel document, it was engendered to be used at toll payments; citizens can also buy bus and train tickets with the MyKad card by transferring money through the ID card⁴⁷. While it contains passport information⁴⁹; it can also be utilized for applying for a passport⁴⁸.

The MyKad ID also serves as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left

<i>Health</i>	For storing : health information ⁴⁷
<i>Trade</i>	For doing : secure transactions via the Public Key Infrastructure ⁴⁷
<i>Identification</i>	For Providing : Proof of identity ⁴⁷

Observation:

While analyzing MyKad and its acceptance among citizens of Malaysia, it is observed that citizens were not convinced about the convenience of MyKad services and were uncertain about its benefits and feel it does not fit into their lifestyle⁴⁹. An observation here would be to incorporate an initial step into the plan for solving for citizen needs or service delivery; which would entail identifying conventional, unique and citizen set specific pathways (or modes) already in existence which have the potential to address said citizen need or are already addressing the same in some manner (i.e., assessing how citizens are fulfilling said need now). And to further amplify or mold the said pathway or mode to achieve successful fulfillment of citizen needs or service delivery. Such modulation could perhaps serve as a better model to ensure citizens accept and adapt to modes of service offered by the government.

Ghana

The Ghana Card is the national identity card of Ghana. Like all identity cards mentioned above, it is also equipped with biometric functionality which takes in the respective fingerprints of the citizens to further identify them and deliver services based on said identification mechanism.

Finance : Opening a bank account, withdrawing money and receiving money transfers and receiving loans are some services in which the Ghana card serves as an identification document allowing citizens to perform such monetary transactions seamlessly with the help of the Ghana card by proving their identity⁵⁰

Travel : In the sphere of travel, citizens utilize the Ghana card to prove their identity while applying for a driving license and passport; proving one's identity while traveling is also possible through the mentioned government identity card⁵⁰.

Services : The National Identification Authority of Ghana conveys that a Ghana Card is mandatory for all accessing all cases which require an individual to prove their identity⁵⁰; this makes it critical for citizens to ensure they acquire said card so they aren't left out of the regular economy.

The Ghana card also serves as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left

<i>Health</i>	For Accessing : healthcare services by government ⁵⁰
<i>Pension</i>	For Accessing Provident Fund or PF ⁵⁰
<i>Land</i>	For Registering Land ⁵⁰
<i>Education</i>	For Accessing : enrollment in schools ⁵⁰
<i>Trade</i>	For Registering a business ⁵⁰
<i>Communication</i>	For Accessing mobile services related to a SIM ⁵³
<i>Voting</i>	For accessing voter id ⁵²

Observation

The experience of women attempting to access Ghana Card consists of the following : issues with unreliable internet connectivity, long waiting times; with the consequence of being cut off from accessing digital payments until one gets the Ghana Card are some of the experiences of women citizens with the Ghana Card⁸¹. Assessing these facets of the citizen experience with respect to the Ghana Card, the observation made with respect to Aadhaar about creating malleable process bodies which adapt to ensure seamless service delivery could also apply here. Government process bodies responsible for service delivery (in this case, the bodies enabling registration for Ghana Card), could be more effective in successful delivery of service if they onboard citizens to their services in modes citizens are comfortable with instead of a singular fixed protocol to achieve their goal.

Philippines

The Philippine Identification System ID or the PhilSys ID is the National ID provided to the citizens of the Philippines and foreign residents in the Philippines, the services citizens can avail using the PhilSys ID range from receipt of social welfare benefits to banking services to even admission to a government hospital⁵⁴.

Finance : The PhilSys ID can be utilized by citizens to validate their identity while they access any financial services, the ID also plays a role as an identity proof while citizens engage with tax related transactions, employment related transactions⁵⁴

Travel : In the sphere of travel, citizens utilize the PhilSys ID card to prove their identity while applying for a driving license and passport⁵⁴.

The PhilSys ID also serves as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left⁵⁴,

<i>Health</i>	For Accessing : entry to hospital or health center, public or private
<i>Education</i>	For Accessing : enrollment in all schools and colleges
<i>Employment</i>	For Applying to jobs
<i>Social Security</i>	For Proving eligibility to access welfare benefits
<i>Governance</i>	For Proving identity while engaging with the government services
<i>Voting</i>	For Validating identity during voter registration

Observations:

While a recurring pattern of utilizing the ID for varied government service delivery initiatives is seen across countries (along with Philippines), Philippines also falls under the list of countries who have also taken the step of taking preemptive measures to protect personal information of citizens online; it has passed a data protection law first before passing the ID law to safeguard citizen data in government systems but in private systems.⁵⁸ However it could still be vulnerable to cases of government employees utilizing citizen contact information they are not authorized to access⁸²; therefore mechanisms to carry out transparency measures which convey and update how the citizen data is being protected (in this case with the ID) and utilized could serve to bolster citizen confidence and could further ensure effective citizen identifying data protection (in this case w.r.t the ID).

Uganda

The national identity card of Uganda was created with the goal of providing registration to individuals Uganda to enable successful identification and seamless delivery of services.

Finance : The National ID is utilized by citizens to validate their identity for activities like filing for Income Tax returns, paying taxes, applying for insurance and for financial services performed by them⁵⁵

Travel : The Ugandan national ID can be utilized to validate a citizen's identity while applying for a passport⁵⁵.

The Ugandan National ID also serves as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left⁵⁵,

<i>Pension</i>	For Accessing Provident Fund or PF
<i>Land</i>	For Purchasing transferring and registering land
<i>Employment</i>	For Authenticating citizen identity
<i>Social Security</i>	For Accessing : government provided welfare services, health education
<i>Voting</i>	For Validating identity as a voter

Observations :

The Ugandan National ID has been observed to increase the likelihood of adopting and using digital money services (via mobile, accessing a SIM is only possible by presenting the National ID) leading to financial inclusion for women , it is also seen that women are 30% less likely to transact using said digital money services than men⁵⁹. While it is seen that ID acts as a positive factor enabling women, it can be seen that it is also in a way reflecting the existing problems in Uganda with respect to gender wise financial inclusion. The National ID being made mandatory to access a host of services from accessing social security benefits to enrolling in a college creates a real risk of exclusion⁸⁴ further exacerbating existing problems faced by citizens. An observation here would be to enable citizens to validate their identity through alternative forms of identity verification and create mechanisms which cater to citizen specific ID needs, for example enabling utilization of an id form which a specific set of citizen beneficiaries are already using.

Kenya

The National ID card of Kenya was created with the goal of providing a unique identity to every person, both citizens and foreigners registered in the national population register, the ID aims to support seamless disbursement of all national identification cards, refugee cards, foreigner certificates, birth and death certificates, driving licenses, work permits, passport and foreign travel documentation, student identification cards issued under the Births and Deaths Registration Act (Cap. 149), the Basic Education Act (Cap. 211), the Registration of Persons Act

(Cap. 107), the Refugees Act (Cap. 173), the Traffic Act (Cap. 403) and the Kenya Citizenship and Immigration Act (Cap. 170) and all other forms of government issued identification documentation as may be specified by gazette notice by the Cabinet Secretary⁶⁰

Finance : The Kenyan digital ID serves as an identifier to access services related to the Revenue authority of Kenya⁶²

Travel : The National ID card can be utilized to validate one's identity while traveling within select parts of African communities⁶².

The Kenyan National ID also serves as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left⁶²

<i>Education</i>	For Enrolment in Educational Institutions
<i>Death Certificate</i>	The Digital ID number would also act as a death certificate number
<i>Governance</i>	For Accessing services provided by government (insurance, social security)

Observations :

While Kenya's digital ID aims to make service delivery more seamless, this goal has been hampered by the displayed gaps with respect to the protection of data gathered for said ID.

The digital ID initiative has also been blocked by the High Court of Kenya in the past due to concerns with respect to data protection⁸⁵. Pursuing an approach which ensures citizen data remains on respective citizen's local servers and does not reside with any other party could perhaps prove to be an effective way to safeguard citizen data.

Argentina

The Argentinian National Identity document is issued to citizens of Argentina and temporary or permanent aliens. It can be utilized for services which range from voting to military service; it contains an electronic chip and the biometric data of the cardholder along with a QR code holding respective cardholder information⁶³

Travel : The Argentinian National ID card aims to enable seamless international travel to select countries by providing an ID which acts as an interoperable travel document which can be easily validated by countries⁶³

The Argentinian National ID also serves as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left^{61,63}

<i>Voting</i>	For Validating one's identity to vote
<i>Communication</i>	For validating one's identity via digital signature, which can be authenticated by checking the private key (used by signer while signing) with the public key (used by person wishing to authenticate said digital signature)
<i>Government Benefits</i>	For accessing services and benefits provided by government

Observations :

While the digital services provided by the government enable citizens to seamlessly avail them, the availability and further use of citizen ID data by inter-governmental agencies from the law enforcement to provincial authorities raises concerns about the extent and purposes to which such citizen ID data will be utilized⁸⁷. Pursuing an approach which prioritizes citizen privacy by restricting access of citizen ID data to government agencies and providing such access based on a transparent set of principles which citizens are made aware of, could lead to an ecosystem where citizens and state can trust each other without citizen mistrust (which might discourage use of ID systems).

Brazil

The national identity card of Brazil is viewed as the official identity document of the country, it is available in physical and digital modes; and was aimed to curb the divergent information for citizen identification, it is valid throughout the national territory and can be used to validate one's identity for all legal purposes and enables citizens to access public services using the same

The Brazil digital ID could serve as a proof of identification and enables access to the varied services from accessing one's digital work portfolio to digitally signing documents⁶⁷; below are some more services in the mentioned fields on the left⁶⁵

<i>Finance</i>	For Declaring Income tax
<i>Vaccination</i>	For Accessing Vaccination card
<i>Digital Wallet</i>	For Proving one's identity to access Digital wallet
<i>Education</i>	For Enrolling in educational programs
<i>Social Security</i>	For Accessing welfare benefits provided by the government

<i>Governance</i>	For Accessing services provided by the government (ex: state and municipal level service portals)
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Observations :

The Brazilian government's push to provide a majority of services in a digital mode creates a real risk of exclusion, issues like connectivity and a lack of digital identity due to lack of required documents to avail one are some factors which are contributing to citizen exclusion⁶⁶, further kerning their access to said services. The sharing and usage of citizen ID data between inter-governmental agencies for purposes other than which it was collected for; shows that such activities are not adhering to the country's data protection legislation. An approach where provision of digital services is not done at the cost of deprioritizing other service delivery modes certain citizen segments are comfortable with; along with transparently communicating the citizen ID data storage and utilization processes to citizens coupled with a focus on ensuring citizen privacy by delinking citizen ID data from government services could lead to an increased level of citizen trust and usage in the ID.

Chile

The government of Chile's ID acts as a key enabler to access varied government services from pension to even accessing the government's vaccination portal; over 1600 public services can be accessed using said id⁷¹

The services accessible by the Chilean national ID as observed from the government website show that National ID could serve as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left⁶⁸

<i>Finance</i>	To Renegotiate procedure related to Bankruptcy
<i>Travel</i>	To access transport permits
<i>Land</i>	To access subsidies related to housing or even lease grants
<i>Agriculture</i>	To register oneself to import specific goods, access agricultural subsidies
<i>Governance</i>	To access most services delivered by government
<i>Trade</i>	To Register a business, apply for a license for a trade
<i>Identification</i>	For Authenticating one's identity and place of residence

Observations:

The Chilean ID, while enabling citizens to benefit from digitally accessing multiple services, is often also a tool of citizen profiling by private entities like supermarkets, pharmacies and more who convey the need for the citizen ID number to access discounts and loyalty programs⁸⁸. While there have been campaigns⁷⁰ to make citizens aware of such practices and the recent Data Protection Law⁸⁹ ensures firms are held accountable towards usage of citizen data; effectively curbing practices which coerce or misguide citizens (example, by conveying they would not be able to access a service without conveying the ID number) by clear public communication (from government) which clarifies such confusion along with mechanisms to intimate the government of such coercive measures would help create a more transparent utilization of ID.

Australia

The Digital ID of Australia serves as a valid identity document which citizens of Australia can utilize to authenticate their identity, the Digital ID Act of 2024 aims to provide individuals with secure, convenient, voluntary and inclusive ways to verify their identity in online transactions with government and businesses;

- (a) to facilitate the inclusion of individuals in digital society by supporting the provision of digital ID services that are accessible for individuals who experience barriers in using such services;
- (b) to promote privacy and the security of personal information used to verify the identity or attributes of individuals;
- (c) to facilitate economic benefits for, and reduce burdens on, the Australian economy by encouraging the use of digital IDs and online services;
- (d) to promote trust in digital ID services amongst the Australian community⁷². [Ref](#)

The services accessible by the Australian Digital ID as observed from the government website show that the Digital ID could serve as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left⁷³

<i>Finance</i>	For Authenticating identity to perform financial transactions
<i>Land</i>	For Renting a property
<i>Social Security</i>	For accessing welfare benefits provided by government (ex: childcare, disaster relief services)
<i>Governance</i>	For accessing government services
<i>Communication</i>	For Signing up for a phone plan

Observations:

While the Digital ID offers access to many citizen services, it contains some gaps; addressing which could lead to an effective ID system. The ID system would be in a centralized mode which could make it more susceptible to attacks, it also wouldn't allow citizens to selectively disclose their information and leaves them vulnerable to being tracked while they access various services⁹⁰. Creation of a mechanism where citizen data does not leave citizen local server along with prioritizing citizen privacy by allowing citizens to control the sharing and visibility of their data could lead to a more effective ID system.

Another safeguard which could help not just the Australian ID but ID systems across countries would be to set up safeguards to protect the right to a citizen's identity⁷⁴, so a citizen's right to service delivery is not impacted. Creating mechanisms which ease and provide alternatives to citizens to prove who they are along with recognising that such right to identity cannot be compromised could lead to an effective utilization of ID.

Japan

The My Number Card is used as an individual identity document in Japan, the My Number card is a 12-digit number designated and provided to all residents in Japan and is managed and kept under specific rules in the areas of social security, taxation and disaster response defined by the law: The My Number Act, the My Number card has an embedded electronic certificate which is utilized to prove citizen identity and can also be used to complete administrative procedures like filing tax online, notifying municipal offices of change of address and it can also be utilized as a health insurance card⁷⁵. It contains cardholder's basic information, such as cardholder's name, address, date of birth, biological sex, Individual Number, as well as a photo of the cardholder; Foreign residents can receive an Individual Number Card after confirming their identity using a photo ID such as their passport⁷⁶.

The My Number Card could serve as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left⁷⁵

<i>Finance</i>	For Filing taxes online
<i>Health</i>	For utilizing it as proof of vaccination
<i>Social Security</i>	For accessing child care, welfare and health care services

<i>Governance</i>	For accessing administrative services
<i>Identification</i>	For validating identity (ex: in place of driver’s license)

Observations:

While observing the experience of citizens with the My Number Card and its utilization; it is seen that citizen concerns with respect to their privacy, the perceived effort required to acquire said card along with a low opinion of the benefits availed from it form some key factors which dissuade citizens from acquiring a card or act as areas of concern for citizens⁷⁷. Apart from communication from the government which helps shed light on simplified access to ID (along with developing trust); identifying citizen use cases which could act as lucrative pulls toward the utilization of the My Number Card could help increase the effectiveness of the ID .

European Union

European electronic identity regulation, 2014 followed by member states of the european union was amended in 2021 to that everyone should always control their digital identity, the EU Digital Identity Wallet was chosen as the means to achieve this goal, the aim was to enable citizens to be able to carry their digital identity with them across the EU, moving seamlessly across borders without ever losing control of their data, with privacy and security at the heart of the project. The regulation entered into force in May 2024; the said wallet aims to fulfill the Digital Decade Policy Programme target of 100% of EU citizens having access to Digital ID by 2030⁷⁸.

The Digital ID, along with digital id wallet could serve as a proof of identification and enables access to the below services in the mentioned fields on the left⁷⁹

<i>Finance</i>	For opening a bank account and authorizing payment transfers
<i>Travel</i>	For accessing digital driver’s license
<i>Education</i>	For accessing digital educational diplomas
<i>Social Security</i>	For accessing social security benefits
<i>Governance</i>	For accessing digital public services
<i>Communication</i>	For Registering a new prepaid SIM
<i>Identity</i>	For Authenticating identity via digital signature

Observations :

Citizen perception of an ID system could play a role in their understanding and use of the said system. This can be seen with the European Digital Wallet where citizens' concerns like their mistrust towards private actors providing ID services and their uncertainty about the scope and usage of wallet leads to a negative perception towards the wallet⁸⁰. Approaches to ID creation and service delivery which focus on catering to use cases which have a high citizen demand along with clear communication of the benefits and a service delivery not limited to certain citizen set preferences (ex: will not work without internet) could result in an identity wallet with more citizen acceptance and usage.

Conclusion

The intent to deliver seamless welfare services has been a key point in the creation of identity documents, some examples of this seem to be India and Japan apart from other countries. While the identity services started with such singular intent, their usage was seemingly allowed across a wide range of citizen use cases, like filing taxes, applying for driver's licenses and more. The European Union's initiative of Digital Identity Wallet which acts as a one stop shop for accessing identity across education, finance and many other sectors across EU, shows us the future direction this sphere is moving towards. While such initiatives aim to fulfill such ambitious goals, the process of adaptation by citizens plays a key role in the success of such initiatives. This is further corroborated by observations from countries Estonia, Malaysia, EU and Japan. Attempting to align the vision behind the creation of IDs with the metric of citizen acceptance could help drive effective adoption of such ID systems. From observations in India, the paper supposes that : Ensuring citizens are able to access ID systems by enabling process bodies to be malleable to citizens' acceptable mode of accessing the ID systems could increase ID usage. The paper also suggests transparency in government communication about citizen identity data use and storage by governments could help build trust in ID systems. Analyzing the countries' ID systems, the paper suggests that citizens enabling process bodies to be malleable to citizens' acceptable mode of accessing the same along with transparency in citizen data use by governments could lead to better citizen use and acceptance of ID.

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References

1. India, Supreme Court. "Writ Petition (Civil) No. 247 of 2017." *UIDAI*, 2017, uidai.gov.in/images/Pan-Aadhaar_Linking.pdf.
2. Ministry of Labour & Employment, India. "Converging Insurance Schemes." Government of India, Ministry of Labour & Employment, 2017, labour.gov.in/sites/default/files/convergence_guidelines_dated_13.11.2017.pdf.
3. Ministry of External Affairs, Passport Seva, India. "Tatkaal Scheme." *Passport Seva, Ministry of External Affairs*, passportindia.gov.in/AppOnlineProject/pdf/Undertaking_for_Tatkaal_Scheme_English.pdf.
4. Ministry of Railways, India. "Book Upto 24 Tickets in a Month by Linking Aadhaar." Indian Railways, contents.irctc.co.in/en/BookUpto12ticketsinamonthbylinkingAadhaar.pdf. Accessed 8 Nov. 2024.
5. Ministry of Road Transport & Highways, India. "Proof Documents for Issuance of Driving License." *Ministry of Road Transport & Highways*, 2023, morth.nic.in/sites/default/files/circulars_document/letter_Proof_documents_for_issuance_of_driving_license_and_registration_certificate_0001.pdf.

6. Federation of Hotel & Restaurant Associations of India. “Aadhaar Verification at Hotels.” Federation of Hotel & Restaurant Associations of India, www.fhrai.com/news_details.aspx?Id=edca3737-c767-4f49-92f3-fb2fcbf0bb0f.
7. Ministry of Petroleum & Natural Gas, India. “Application Process PMUJ Connection.” Ministry of Petroleum & Natural Gas, pmuy.gov.in/ujjwala2.html. Accessed 8 Nov. 2024.
8. Ministry of Human Resource Development, India. “Notification.” Ministry of Education, Government of India, pmposhan.education.gov.in/Files/Aadhar/Aadhar_mdm.pdf.
9. Government of Haryana, India. “Notification of Cash Award Scheme under Aadhaar Act.” Directorate of Elementary Education, Government of Haryana, cdnbbsr.s3waas.gov.in/s3b2ab001909a8a6f04b51920306046ce5/uploads/2021/06/2021061599.pdf.
10. Department of Women and Child Development, India. “Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana .” Department of Women and Child Development, wcd.delhi.gov.in/wcd/pradhan-mantri-matru-vandana-yojana-pmmvy#:~:text=Benefits%20can%20be%20availed%20only,avoid%20any%20duplication%20or%20malpractices.&text=In%20case%20of%20miscarriage%2Fstill,event%20of%20any%20future%20pregnancy.
11. Department of Women and Child Development, India. “Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana .” Department of Women and Child Development, wcd.delhi.gov.in/wcd/pradhan-mantri-matru-vandana-yojana-pmmvy#:~:text=Benefits%20can%20be%20availed%20only,avoid%20any%20duplication%20or%20malpractices.&text=In%20case%20of%20miscarriage%2Fstill,event%20of%20any%20future%20pregnancy.
12. National Medical Commission, Government of India. “Notification.” *National Medical Commission*, www.nmc.org.in/MCIRest/open/getDocument?path=/Documents/Public/Portal/LatestNews/18%20ABHA%20Advisory%20004-06-2024_0001_0001.pdf.
13. National Health Authority, India. “Benefits of ABHA.” National Health Authority, abha.abdm.gov.in/abha/v3/.

14. Ministry of Labour & Employment, EPFO, India. "Mandatory Aadhaar Seeding ." EPFO Ministry of Labour & Employment, Government of India, www.epfindia.gov.in/site_docs/PDFs/Circulars/Y2024-2025/Mandatory_aadhaar_seeding_11062024.pdf.
15. Jeevan Pramaan, Government of India. "Generating Digital Life Certificate." Jeevan Pramaan, jeevanpramaan.gov.in/newassets/docs/Procedures_for_DLC_Ver1_0.pdf.
16. Ministry of Housing & Urban Affairs, India. "Housing for All Mission Guidelines." PMAY, Ministry of Housing & Urban Affairs, 2024, pmay-urban.gov.in/uploads/guidelines/Operational-Guidelines-of-PMAY-U-2.pdf.
17. Ministry of Rural Development, India. "Aadhaar Authentication for Land Registration." Ministry of Rural Development, Department of Land Resources, cdnbbsr.s3waas.gov.in/s3d69116f8b0140cdeb1f99a4d5096ffe4/uploads/2024/01/2024010295062726.pdf.
18. Ministry of Rural Development, India. "MGNREGA." Press Information Bureau, Government of India, pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2068646#:~:text=DBT%20%26%20Aadhar%20Seeding,which%20the%20account%20is%20linked.
19. Attendance Dashboard, Government of India. "Aadhaar for Marking Attendance (Query 6)." Attendance Dashboard, attendance.gov.in/faq/public_faq.
20. Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, India. "Soil Health Card." Press Information Bureau, Government of India, pib.gov.in/PressReleseDetailm.aspx?PRID=1947891®=3&lang=1.
21. Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, India "Operational Guidelines PMFBY." PMFBY Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, pmfby.gov.in/pdf/Revised_Operational_Guidelines.pdf
22. Ministry of Rural Development, India. "Performance of NSAP." Press Information Bureau, Government of India, pib.gov.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=178358
23. Ministry of Law & Justice, India "E-filing Procedure" Ecourts, ecourts.gov.in/ecourts_home/static/manuals/efiling-User-manual.pdf

24. Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises, India “Frequently Asked Questions.” PM Vishwakarma Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises, pmvishwakarma.gov.in/Home/FAQ
25. Unique Identification Authority of India, Government of India “Aadhaar Myth Busters.” Unique Identification Authority of India, uidai.gov.in/en/my-aadhaar/about-your-aadhaar/aadhaar-myth-busters.html
26. DigiLocker, Government of India “Terms of User” DigiLocker, img1.digitallocker.gov.in/circulars/termsfuse/DigiLock_20ToS_August2021_V4.pdf
27. Ministry of External Affairs, Passport Seva, India. “Proof of Address.” *Passport Seva, Ministry of External Affairs*, www.passportindia.gov.in/AppOnlineProject/popuponline/AttachmentAdvisorSub?subDocID=7001&minorFlag=1
28. India, Supreme Court. “Writ Petition (Civil) No. 494 of 2012.” UIDAI, uidai.gov.in/images/news/Judgement_26-Sep-2018.pdf.
29. Chief Election Officer Delhi, India. “Press Release” Chief Electoral Officer Delhi, ceodelhi.gov.in/PDFFolder/PN-Amendment%20PR%2001.08.22.pdf
30. Nair, A., Eskici, B. (2023). Digital Public Services: The Development of Biometric Authentication in India. In: Madon, T., Gadgil, A.J., Anderson, R., Casaburi, L., Lee, K., Rezaee, A. (eds) Introduction to Development Engineering. Springer, Cham. doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86065-3_20
31. Santosh Patoda, Tanu Anand, Sairu Philip, Palanivel Chinnakali, Abinash Mishra, Pruthu Thekkur, Pallavi Indwar, Jaykumari Choudhary, Sofia Noor, Pradip Kumar Jana, Did they receive it? Direct Benefit Transfer to tuberculosis patients in Raigarh district, Chhattisgarh, India - A mixed methods study, *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, Volume 30, 2024, 101790, ISSN 2213-3984, doi.org/10.1016/j.cegh.2024.101790.
32. Republic of Estonia. “e-Identity.” e-Estonia, e-estonia.com/solutions/estonian-e-identity/id-card/
33. Republic of Estonia, Estonian Tax and Customs Board. “About Submitting Income Tax Returns..” Estonian Tax and Customs Board,

emta.ee/en/private-client/foreigner-non-resident/foreigners/declaration-income

34. Republic of Estonia. “Healthcare.” e-Estonia, digiexpo.e-estonia.com/category/healthcare/
35. Republic of Estonia. “e-services & registries.” e-Estonia, digiexpo.e-estonia.com/e-governance/e-services-and-registries/e-child-sport/
36. Republic of Estonia. “e-Governance.” e-Estonia, e-estonia.com/solutions/e-governance/e-democracy/
37. Tsap, V., Lips, S., Draheim, D. (2020). Analyzing eID Public Acceptance and User Preferences for Current Authentication Options in Estonia. In: Kõ, A., Francesconi, E., Kotsis, G., Tjoa, A., Khalil, I. (eds) Electronic Government and the Information Systems Perspective. EGOVIS 2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science(), vol 12394. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58957-8_12
38. Parsovs, Arnis, Solving the Estonian ID Card Crisis: the Legal Issues (May 2020). In: ISCRAM 2020 Conference Proceedings - 17th International Conference on Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management; Blacksburg, Virginia (USA), May 2020, pp. 459–471, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3644664>
39. McGrath, Kathy. “Identity Verification and Societal Challenges: Explaining the Gap Between Service Provision and Development Outcomes.” MIS Quarterly, vol. 40, no. 2, 2016, pp. 485–500. JSTOR, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26628918>. Accessed 9 Nov. 2024.
40. Government of Bangladesh, Department of Information Communication & Technology . “Digital ID For Digital Bangladesh-eID.” Department of Information Communication & Technology, ictd.portal.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/ictd.portal.gov.bd/publications/c79eb060_358e_466e_b1e4_7c47452e84bf/Digital%20ID%20For%20Digital%20Bangladesh-eID%202015.pdf
41. Government of Bangladesh, Bangladesh High Commission London. “E-passport application.” Bangladesh High Commission London, bhclondon.org.uk/e-passport-application#epassport3
42. Government of Bangladesh, myGov. “FAQ” myGov,

mygov.bd/faq-list

43. Government of Bangladesh, myGov. “Government services in one address” myGov, mygov.bd
44. Government of Bangladesh, myGov. “Services acc. to sector : Agriculture” myGov, mygov.bd/services?category=sector&data=service-sector-59
45. Government of Bangladesh, myGov. “Services acc. to sector : Registration & Licensing” myGov, mygov.bd/services?category=sector&data=service-sector-45
46. Government of Bangladesh, myGov. “Services acc. to sector : Grants, Allowances & Loans” myGov, mygov.bd/services?category=sector&data=service-sector-4
47. Government of Malaysia, My Government. “MyKad” My Government, malaysia.gov.my/portal/content/30582
48. Official Portal of Road Transport Department, Malaysia. “Application for Learning License” Official Portal of Road Transport Department, Malaysia, jpj.gov.my/web/main-site/pemandu/-/knowledge_base/pemandu/permohonan-lesen-belajar-memandu-ldl
49. W.H. Loo, Paul H.P. Yeow, S.C. Chong, User acceptance of Malaysian government multipurpose smartcard applications, Government Information Quarterly, Volume 26, Issue 2, 2009, Pages 358-367, ISSN 0740-624X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2008.07.004>.
50. Ghana, National Identification Authority. ”Registration of Ghanians in Ghana” National Identification Authority, nia.gov.gh/service/registration-of-citizens-in-ghana/#:~:text=The%20Ghana%20Card%20makes%20it,to%20Ghana%20without%20a%20visa.
51. Ghana, National Identification Authority. ”FAQs” National Identification Authority, nia.gov.gh/faqs/
52. Ghana, Electoral Commission, “Registration Procedures” Electoral Commission Ghana, ec.gov.gh/registration/

53. Ghana, Ministry of Communication & Digitalisation, “Update on SIM Registration..” National Communications Authority, nca.org.gh/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Update-on-Sim-Registration-Exercise-11-11-2022.pdf
54. Republic of the Philippines, Congress of the Philippines. “Republic Act N.o 11055” Wikimedia, upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/8/87/Republic_Act_No._11055_%2820180806-RA-11055-RRD%29.pdf
55. Uganda, Ministry of ICT & National Guidance. “Registration of Person Act” Ministry of ICT & National Guidance, ict.go.ug/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Registration-of-Person-Act-2015.pdf
56. Government of Kenya, Digital ID. “Maisha Digital ID” Digital ID, did.ecitizen.go.ke/
57. Effah, J., & Debrah, E. (2018). Biometric technology for voter identification: The experience in Ghana. *The Information Society*, 34(2), 104–113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01972243.2017.1414720>
58. Government of Philippines, National Privacy Commission, “Data Privacy Act” National Privacy Commission, privacy.gov.ph/data-privacy-act/
59. Mugume, Regean, and Enock WN Bulime. "Post-COVID-19 recovery for African economies: Lessons for digital financial inclusion from Kenya and Uganda." *African Development Review* 34 (2022): S161-S176.
60. Government of Kenya. “Registration of Persons” Kenya Law, [kenyalaw.org:8181/exist/kenyalex/actview.xql?actid=CAP.%20107#sec_8](https://kenyalaw.org/8181/exist/kenyalex/actview.xql?actid=CAP.%20107#sec_8)
61. Borak, Masha. “Buenos Aires’ moves from centralized to decentralized digital identity with QuarkID” Biometric update.com, www.biometricupdate.com/202410/buenos-aires-moves-from-centralized-to-decentralize-d-digital-identity-with-quarkid#:~:text=The%20framework%20was%20developed%20in,under%20the%20Apache%202.0%20license.
62. Indeje, David . ”Understanding Maisha Namba: Kenya’s New Digital Identity System” KICTANet,

www.kictanet.or.ke/understanding-maisha-namba-kenyas-new-digital-identity-system/

63. Government of Argentina. “Functionalities of the electronic DNI (DNIe)” Google Drive, drive.google.com/file/d/1pI0eDHPE2zcc7gnJSvgyIQ7aA9ouAPtt/view
64. Chudnovsky, M., & Peeters, R. (2022). A cascade of exclusion: administrative burdens and access to citizenship in the case of Argentina’s National Identity Document. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 88(4), 1068-1085. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852320984541>
65. Mesquita, Hudson Vinicius. “Gov.br Digital ID” Global Digital ID Repository, www.dpi.global/globaldpi/gbr_digital_id#:~:text=Use%20Cases,and%20municipal%20public%20service%20portals
66. Bioni B, Garrote M, Meira M, Paschoalini N. The digitization of the Brazilian national identity system: A descriptive and qualitative analysis of its information architecture. *Data & Policy*. 2022;4:e22. doi:10.1017/dap.2022.14
67. Government of Brazil. “Where to use the gov.br account” gov.br, <https://www.gov.br/governodigital/pt-br/identidade/conta-gov-br/onde-usar-a-conta-govbr/onde-usar-a-conta-gov.br>
68. Government of Chile. “Tramites” Clave Unica, claveunica.gob.cl/tramites
69. Privacy International. “Liliana: “If you don’t have RUT, you can’t do it.” Privacy International, <https://privacyinternational.org/case-study/2545/liliana-if-you-dont-have-rut-you-cant-do-it>
70. Araya, Valentina Camilla . “NODOYMIRUT” Datos Protegidos, <https://datosprotegidos.org/no-doy-mi-rut/>
71. InvestChile. “Digital identification: A key to inclusive growth in Chile” InvestChile, <https://blog.investchile.gob.cl/digital-identification-chile>
72. Commonwealth of Australia. “Digital ID Bill 2024” Parliament of Australia, https://parinfo.aph.gov.au/parInfo/search/display/display.w3p;db=LEGISLATION;id=legislation%2Fbills%2Fs1404_third-senate%2F0001;query=Id%3A%22legislation%2Fbill%2Fs1404_third-senate%2F0000%22

73. Government of Australia. "Digital ID for Everyday Life" Australia's Digital ID System, <https://www.digitalidsystem.gov.au/digital-id-for-everyday-life>
74. Sullivan, C. (2013). Digital Citizenship and the Right to Identity in Australia. *Federal Law Review*, 41(3), 557-584. <https://doi.org/10.22145/flr.41.3.7>
75. Tsukuba City, City Services Division. "To Everyone Who Obtained a My Number Card" City of Tsukuba, <https://www.city.tsukuba.lg.jp/material/files/group/28/eigo.pdf>
76. Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications Digital Agency. "Information Regarding the Individual Number System" Individual Number Card, <https://www.kojinbango-card.go.jp/hpsv/wpmng/assets/pdf/download/pamphlet-for-foreigners-en.pdf>
77. Yamaguchi, Shinichi, et al. "An Empirical Analysis of Psychological Factors in Japanese Individual Number Card Acquisition Behavior: Examination of effective promotion measures." Available at SSRN 4822033 (2024).
78. European Commission. "About the Initiative" EU Digital Identity Wallet, <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/sites/display/EUDIGITALIDENTITYWALLET/About+the+initiative>
79. European Commission. "The many use cases of EU Digital Identity Wallets" EU Digital Identity Wallet, <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/sites/display/EUDIGITALIDENTITYWALLET/The+many+use+cases+of+the+EU+Digital+Identity+Wallet>
80. Lukkien, Bert, Nitesh Bharosa, and Mark De Reuver. "Barriers for developing and launching digital identity wallets." *Proceedings of the 24th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research*. 2023.
81. Batambuze, Ibrahim., Akuetteh, Teki. "Digitization efforts in Ghana have driven opportunity. But is it helping – or hindering – women?" Digital Impact Alliance, <https://dial.global/ghana-digitization-efforts-driving-opportunity-helping-hindering-women/>
82. Homes, David. "Data Privacy and the 2018 Philippine Identification System Act" F5,

<https://www.f5.com/labs/articles/cisotociso/data-privacy-and-the-2018-philippine-identification-system-act>

83. Bongomin, G. O. C., Akol Malinga, C., Amani Manzi, A., & Balinda, R. (2023). Agent liquidity: A catalyst for mobile money banking among the unbanked poor population in rural sub-Saharan Africa. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2203435>
84. Bhalla, Nita . “Uganda sued over digital ID system that excludes millions” Reuters,
<https://www.reuters.com/article/markets/commodities/feature-uganda-sued-over-digital-id-system-that-excludes-millions-idUSL3N2X32RG/>
85. Burt, Chris. “History repeats with Kenyan High Court blocking Maisha Namba for lack of DPIA” Biometric update.com,
<https://www.biometricupdate.com/202312/history-repeats-with-kenyan-high-court-blocking-maisha-namba-for-lack-of-dpia>
86. Gikunju, Washington. “Broken system: Inside Kenya’s ID crisis” Nation,
<https://nation.africa/kenya/news/broken-system-inside-kenya-s-id-crisis-4515168>
87. Rodriguez, Katitza. “Biometrics in Argentina: Mass Surveillance as a State Policy” EFF,
<https://www.eff.org/deeplinks/2012/01/biometrics-argentina-mass-surveillance-state-policy>
88. Calderon, Martin. “Are you a product? Protected Data Foundation launches #NoDoyMiRUT campaign” FayerWayer,
https://www-fayerwayer-com.translate.googleusercontent.com/2018/07/Cambridge%20Analytics/no-doy-rut-chilenos/?_x_tr_sl=es&_x_tr_tl=en&_x_tr_hl=en&_x_tr_pto=sc
89. Government of Chile. “Constitution of the Republic of Chile, Art. 19 N° 4” DLA Piper,
<https://www.dlapiperdataprotection.com/index.html?t=law&c=CL>
90. Nanda, Ashish., Jeong, Jongkil Jay., Doss, Robin. “Australia’s new digital ID scheme falls short of global privacy standards.” *The Conversation*,
<https://theconversation.com/australias-new-digital-id-scheme-falls-short-of-global-privacy-standards-heres-how-it-can-be-fixed-241797#:~:text=This%20means%20users'%20interactions%20with,and%20potentially%20profile%20their%20behaviours.>
91. Trulioo. “100,000 years of Identity verification..” Trulioo,

<https://www.trulioo.com/blog/identity-verification/infographic-the-history-of-id-verification#:~:text=Personal%20identification%20numbers,and%20governments%20around%20the%20world.>

92. T. Jerzak, Connor. “A Brief History of National ID cards” FXB Center, <https://fxb.harvard.edu/2015/11/12/a-brief-history-of-national-id-cards#:~:text=One%20precursor%20to%20national%20ID,%20religion%20for%20discriminatory%20purposes>).
93. Agar, Jon. “Identity cards in Britain..” History and Policy, <https://www.historyandpolicy.org/policy-papers/papers/identity-cards-in-britain-past-experience-and-policy-implications>
94. Katina Michael, M.G. Michael Historical Lessons on ID Technology and the Consequences of an Unchecked Trajectory. Prometheus. 2006. Vol 24(4): 365-377. DOI: 10.1080/08109020601029938
95. Williams, Colin. (2022). Comparative study of the use of social identity cards in the construction sector in various European countries.
96. HUSZ O. Bank Identity: Banks, ID Cards, and the Emergence of a Financial Identification Society in Sweden. Enterprise & Society. 2018;19(2):391-429. doi:10.1017/eso.2017.43
97. Wihlborg, E., Gustafsson, M. S, Söderström, F., Hedström, K., (2015), Constructing identities: Professional use of eID in public organisations, Transforming Government, 9(2), 143-158. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TG-11-2013-0049>
98. Government of India. “Supreme Court Allows Aadhaar as 12th Identity Document for Bihar Voter List Revision.” *News onair*, 2025, www.newsonair.gov.in/supreme-court-allows-aadhaar-as-12th-identity-document-for-bihar-voter-list-revision/.

